

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

ASSESSMENT OF MORPHOLOGICAL DIFFERENCES IN FRUITS OF *SUAEDA* (*SUAEDA* FORSSK. EX SCOP.) SPECIES IN THE FLORA OF AZERBAIJAN REPUBLIC

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Abstract

The study of *Suaeda* genus is of particular importance in the taxonomy of the family Amaranthaceae (formerly Chenopodiaceae). This article presents the results of a comparative morphological analysis of the fruits of different *Suaeda* species in the territory of Azerbaijan Republic. Morphometric parameters of the fruits (shape, seed mass, width, length, pericarp characteristics) were studied in species such as *S. altissima* (L.) Pall., *S. maritima* (L.) Dumort. (\approx *S. prostrata*), *S. dendroides* C.A.Mey (Moq.), and *S. microphylla* Pall. The results revealed significant interspecific differences in fruit morphology, which reflect the adaptive traits of the species to diverse ecological habitats. By studying the biodiversity and ecological roles of halophytic species in saline habitats, the research supports the conservation and sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems and biodiversity (SDG 15- Life on Land).

Keywords: SDG 13 – Climate Action, SDG 15- Life on Land, fruit, *Suaeda*, Amaranthaceae, carpological data, halophytes, morphology.

Introduction

The genus *Suaeda* Forssk. ex Scop. (family Amaranthaceae) comprises halophytic plants that are widespread in saline and semi-saline ecosystems [4,6]. In Azerbaijan, species of this genus play a crucial role in soil stabilization and biodiversity maintenance in coastal and inland ecosystems. The morphological characteristics of fruits are of diagnostic importance in the taxonomy of *Suaeda*, and also reflect the adaptive strategies of species to varying ecological conditions [1,2].

Understanding the morphological adaptations of halophytes such as *Suaeda* contributes to climate resilience and mitigation strategies in arid and saline ecosystems increasingly affected by climate change (SDG 13 – Climate Action).

The aim of the present work is to assess the variability of fruit morphological traits in dominant *Suaeda* species found in Azerbaijan. Under conditions of fluctuating humidity, temperature, and salinity, *Suaeda* species exhibit high ecological plasticity [8,10].

In most species of *Suaeda*, the fruit is a one-seeded dry capsule, less commonly a nut-like or fleshy pseudoberry. The ovary is superior and unilocular. Fruits are generally indehiscent, increasing their resistance to environmental stress. The size of the fruits ranges from 0.8 to 2.5 mm, with shapes varying from rounded to reniform and asymmetrically flattened. The color of mature fruits varies from brown to dark brown or black, sometimes with a purplish or reddish tint. The surface may be smooth, wrinkled, reticulate, and often covered with a waxy coating that reduces water loss.

Carpology, a subdiscipline of plant morphology, which studies the structure, classification, and development of fruits and seeds, provides insights into the morphogenesis and ontogeny of fruits and seeds, their dispersal patterns, and supports the development of effective identification keys [5,9].

Each fruit typically contains one anatropous seed with a large, curved embryo occupying most of the seed volume. Endosperm is usually absent. The seed coat is dense, often glossy, smooth, or slightly ornamented. This structure serves as a protective adaptation against dehydration and salt stress. The embryo is usually spirally curved, which is characteristic of subfamily Chenopodioideae.

Despite belonging to the same genus, the fruits of some species show significant morphological variation. Examples of species-specific traits include:

- *S. maritima* (L.) Dumort. (\approx *S. prostrata*) - rounded, smooth fruits, approx. 1.3 mm;
- *S. heterophylla* Bunge ex Boiss - kidney-shaped, slightly asymmetric fruits, approx. 2.0 mm;
- *S. altissima* (L.) Pall. - large, grooved fruits up to 2.2 mm with pronounced surface relief.

Differences in fruit morphology often correlate with the species' ecological preferences, making these traits useful for species identification and ecological-geographical comparisons [11]. Fruit morphology in these species has adaptive significance. The fruit coat in most species is poorly permeable, preventing salt penetration and water loss, which is vital under saline conditions [3,7]. Small fruit size facilitates autochorous and anemochorous dispersal. The indehiscent nature of the fruits enhances their longevity in the soil.

In some species, such as *Suaeda maritima* subsp. *Salsa* (L.) Soó (\approx *S. salsa*, (L.) Pall.) environmental variability leads to morphological changes in the fruit: in more saline soils, fruits tend to be smaller with thicker pericarps. This demonstrates a high degree of phenotypic plasticity [12].

The genus *Suaeda* (family Amaranthaceae) comprises halophytic plants widely distributed in saline habitats across Asia, Europe, and North Africa. One of the well-studied representatives of this genus is *Suaeda salsa*, which exhibits pronounced phenotypic plasticity

-the ability to modify morphological and physiological traits in response to external factors such as soil salinity, moisture, temperature, and light intensity.

Studies have shown that in *S. salsa*, as in other halophytes, the degree of soil salinity significantly affects fruit size, seed mass, and pericarp thickness. Under high salinity conditions, fruits become smaller, likely as a result of general plant stress, reduced tissue water retention capacity, and limited nutrient availability. As salinity increases, the pericarp (fruit wall) becomes thicker. This adaptation may play a protective role by reducing transpiration and shielding the embryo from ionic stress.

A decrease in total seed mass is also observed, which correlates with the reduced availability of resources under stressful environmental conditions. The integration of morphological and anatomical data allows for reliable differentiation of species, including microvariants and populations.

Fruit morphology in *Suaeda* species serves as a key taxonomic and eco-adaptive parameter. The structural features of the fruit reflect both phylogenetic differences among species and their plastic responses to environmental stressors [13]. Studying these traits enhances the accuracy of plant identification, facilitates monitoring of population dynamics, and contributes to understanding the mechanisms of halophyte resilience in saline and arid ecosystems.

Increased soil salinity leads to an increase in pericarp thickness, likely serving a protective function by reducing transpiration and shielding the embryo from ionic stress. A decrease in seed mass under such conditions correlates with limited resource availability and general plant stress.

The integration of morphological and anatomical data enables reliable differentiation of species, including within microvariants and populations. Fruit morphology in *Suaeda* species is a significant taxonomic and eco-adaptive parameter. Structural features of the fruit reflect both phylogenetic divergence and plasticity in response to environmental stressors [13].

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